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ANALYSIS OF THE DISTRIBUTIONAL PATTERN OF INFRASTRUCTURAL FACILITIES IN EGUME COMMUNITY, DEKINA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF KOGI STATE

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Abstract: *The study analyzed the distributional pattern of infrastructural facilities in Egume community, Dekina local government area of Kogi State, and brought into focus the level of spatial imbalance in infrastructural development. Primary data were generated from the field using Global Positioning System (GPS) and questionnaire. A total number of 204 copies of questionnaire were distributed and 200 copies were retrieved. The data were analyzed, using descriptive statistics of frequencies and percentages in presenting results of specific objectives of the study. Point data was also presented in form of map which shows the locations of the various infrastructures within the study area. Nearest neighbour analysis (NNA) was performed using Geographic Information System (GIS) in order to determine the distributional pattern of the specific infrastructures. The study showed the mean score for political reason on likert scale to be 1.6 (which was less than 2.60) indicating that infrastructures in the community were not there as a result of political reasons. Profit making was 2.6 which is still lower than the accepted value, meaning that the respondents do not agree with that. Security reasons having a scale of 1.8 was also rejected, Traditional ruler's decision gave a likert mean score of 3.2 which was accepted, suggesting that respondents are in agreement that most of the infrastructures were attracted by the traditional rulers. In addition, the study discovered that some of these infrastructures are clustered, suggesting the need for equity and fairness distribution of infrastructure in order to avoid lopsidedness. Based on the findings of this study, it was suggested that proper attention of the government is needed on the provision of infrastructural facilities in the study area and other rural areas as well.*

Keyword: Distribution, Pattern, Infrastructure, Development and Community

INTRODUCTION

The role of infrastructural facilities in the overall economic growth and development of an area cannot be overemphasized. United Nation (2011) remarked that infrastructure plays a critical role in poverty reduction, economic growth and employment for the masses. The problem of infrastructure and the development of rural areas have continued to be topical in Nigeria. Nigeria's internal disparity between rural and urban areas still remains very high even after several national and regional development efforts (Olayiwola & Adeleye, 2005). Measured in terms of

quality of living, social opportunities, physical facilities, human development and standard of living, the overall score for rural areas still stands very low in comparison with its urban counterparts. The observed internal inequalities in socio-economic development in Nigeria, as in other unindustrialized countries, are linked to the backgrounds of development dating to the colonial era (Calderon, 2009). There is unequal access to productive resources, and basic infrastructures such as schools, health centres, potable water, good feeder roads, culverts, storage and irrigation facilities (Adefila, 2013). Many parts of rural Nigeria

are characterized by unreliable access feeder roads, light failure or epileptic power supply, inadequate basic health facilities, lack of decent housing, educational institution, recreational facilities among (Olayiwola & Adeleye, 2005). In addition, inadequate and low qualities of infrastructures could have serious implication for welfare and persistence of poverty in our society. It is a consensus among scholars (Ndulu, 2006; Calderon & Serve, 2008; Egbetokun, 2009) that infrastructures are the criteria for the success of public and private efforts aimed at accelerating economic development. It is obvious that one cannot expect rapid socio-economic development without adequate provision for infrastructural facilities. (Omofonmwan, 2004) remarked that one of the critical factors that contributed to the high level of rural poverty is the inadequate infrastructural facilities.

Several authors have carried out researches on rural development among which are; Madu (2007) investigated the underlying factors of rural development pattern in Nsukka Region of south-eastern Nigeria. Using questionnaires for data collection and also chi-square for data analysis, the study revealed that, rural areas are deprived of basic amenities and concluded that government should ensure proper monitoring for any given project. Similarly, Ajala & Adeyinka (2005) indicated in their study of accessibility to healthcare facilities in Osun State, that serious inadequacy of health facilities and services exists in rural areas which results in many preventable deaths among rural people. Olayiwola & Adeleye (2005) investigated and documented a comprehensive report on rural infrastructural development in Nigeria between 1960 and 1990 pointing out the problems and challenges responsible for infrastructural variability in a given region.

All these studies examined and explained the problem of rural infrastructure and services while focusing more on either the availability of the physical infrastructure or their spatial distribution, most of these studies did not look at more than one facility using questionnaires, and did not work on this present study area.

It is in the light of the above that this current study is hinged analyzing the distributional pattern of infrastructure in Egume, Dekina Local Government Area of Kogi State. The aim was achieved with the following objectives: (i) analyses of the distributional pattern of infrastructural facilities; and (ii) identification of the factors responsible for the provision and distributional pattern of the infrastructure in the study area. The study is confined to four major infrastructural facilities namely; potable water supply, electricity, schools and Health centres as social infrastructural facilities. These facilities are the major infrastructures in the study area.

STUDY AREA

The study area is Egume in Dekina Local Government area (LGA) and it lies between latitude $7^{\circ} 28'$ and $7^{\circ} 32'$ North of the Equator and longitude $7^{\circ} 09'$ and $7^{\circ} 12'$ East of the Greenwich Meridian. It is on the south eastern direction of Lokoja (capital of Kogi State) and the bearing of Dekina from Lokoja is 1350 and it is one of the oldest LGAs in Nigeria. It is located in the Eastern part of Kogi State and shares common boundary with Ofu, Ankpa, Omala and Bassa LGAs. (Figures 1 and 2). Dekina LGA lies within tropical hinterland, the climate region is characterized partly by double and single maximum rainfall patter with about four months of dry season in the afternoon during the wet season. Rainy season occur between April through October and the peak is September.

Figure 1: Kogi State showing Dekina Local Government Area
Source: Geographical and Information System Laboratory, PAAU (2025)

Figure 2: Egume Community in Dekina LGA
Source: Geographical and Information System Laboratory, PAAU (2025)

Dekina LGA is located within the southern guinea savannah zone, species common to the northern guinea savannah also occur here but is not as much as that of the northern guinea savannah mostly because of man impact. The distribution of tress, grass etc. is determined by factors such as; fire, Demographic pressure, patterns of cultivation among others. Trees found here do adapt to dry conditions (deciduous) and they shed their leaves in the dry season to control evapotranspiration (Ifatimehin & Ufauah, 2006).

Based on the 2006 population census the population of Dekina was 260,968 (NPC, 2006). The indigenes of Dekina are the Igala speaking people with a couple of Yorubas, Fulanis, Igbos, and Hausas who are non-indigenes. The major means of communication is Igala and the English language and the dominant religions are Christianity, Islamic and the traditional religion (Ifatimehin & Ufauah, 2006).

Dekina in 2001/2002 occupied an estimated total land area of 11.07506qkm as compared to about 2.25sqkm in 1974. A major part of the Area (62.28%) is devoted to residential land use (inclusive of residential in prominence in the university). This is followed in prominence by services accounting for as high as 23.27%, the bulk of which is taken by educational land use as either promoted by missionary activities in the town or enhanced by the establishment of the university. Other uses worthy of note are cultivation/green area (jointly accounting for 7.94%) and transportation (3.64%) (Ifatimehin & Ufauah, 2006).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Reconnaissance survey was carried out to examine the infrastructural facilities in the study area and their year of establishment. This method is in agreement with Ajibade (2004) where he pointed out that reconnaissance survey is particularly required for the determination of locations where samples will be taken for analysis. Thus, reconnaissance survey was carried out to generate data on type of water supply, the number of bore holes, number of schools, (nursery, primary, secondary and tertiary institutions), data on health care centres, data on electricity supply and the coordinate of the infrastructural facilities. The population of Egume according to the 1991 National Population Census was 12,589 persons which was projected to 2024 using 2.61% annual growth rate which gave a population of 25,374 persons. Purposive random sampling technique was employed to collect relevant data necessary for the research based on respondents' personal opinion regarding the state of the rural infrastructure in their community. A sample size 204 respondents was arrived at using the formula of Taro Yamani (1967). The instruments used for the study included, geospatial technologies such as Global Positioning System (GPS), Geographic Information System (GIS), Hewlett Packard (HP) 655, ArcGIS 10.5 and MS Excel and SPSS.

The analysis was subjected to descriptive statistics, where frequency, percentage were used in presenting the specific objectives of the study, point data was also presented in form of map which shows the locations of the various infrastructures within the study areas. A nearest neighbour analysis was performed, using G.I.S in other to determine the distributional pattern of the specific infrastructures.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sex	Male	141	70.5
	Female	59	29.5
	Total	200	100.0
Age	20-25	57	28.5
	26-30	116	58.0
	31-35	9	4.5
	36-40	6	3.0
	41-45	7	3.5
	Above 45	5	2.5
	Total	200	100.0
Marital status	Single	98	49.0
	Married	101	50.5
	Separated	1	.5
	Total	200	100.0
Educational	No formal education	2	1.0
	Primary school	3	1.5
	Secondary school	27	13.5
	Tertiary	168	84.0
	Total	200	100.0
Income Level	No fixed income	141	70.5
	Below (N18,000) minimum wage	29	14.5
	N18,000-N30,000	22	11.0
	Above N30,000	8	4.0
	Total	200	100.0
Occupation	Unemployed	10	5.0
	Trading	91	45.5
	Civil Service	38	19.0
	Farming	61	30.5
	Total	200	100.0
Length of stay	0-5 years	9	4.5
	6-10 years	8	4.0
	11-15 years	6	3.0
	16-20 years	5	2.5
	21-25 years	68	34.0
	Above 25 years	104	52.0
	Total	200	100.0
Household size	1-3	105	52.5
	4-6	64	32.0
	7-10	31	15.5
	Total	200	100.0

Source: Author’s Data Compilation 2025

The study as shown on Table 1 revealed that 70.5% of the population selected were male, while 29.5% were female. This is an indication of the role men play in agitating for infrastructural development. The finding further revealed that 116 respondents representing 58.0% of the respondents were between ages 26-30 years; while 28.5% were between ages 20-25 years. This implies that the sampled population were the matured mind who are aware of the happening around their environment. Age is expected to play a significant role as maturity could affect level of awareness. Schultz et al. (2005) as well as Mayer & Frantz (2004) is Bulus (2014) opined that the higher one's age, the more the person is concerned about the environment. This implies that older residents are expected to be more environmentally conscious than the younger counterparts.

The study further revealed that 50.5% of the respondents were married, while 49.0% were single and 0.5% were separated. This simply means that majority of the respondents are matured and are aware of the advantages of infrastructures in an area. This can be linked to the work of Schultz et al. (2005) in (Bulus 2014) who said, maturity could affect level of environmental awareness. 52.5% of the respondents had household size of 1-3 persons per family, 32.0% had 4-6, and 15.5% had 7-10 persons per family. This implies that majority of the respondents had a small household size.

A large percentage of the respondents had tertiary as their education status (84.0%) as revealed by the study and shown on Table 1. Educational status of the respondents plays a significant role in environmental awareness. Studies such as Bulus (2014) as well as Adeoye et al, (2011) opined that educated people are more concerned about the environment and place more emphasis on preserving the environment. The study also

reveals that 13.5% of the respondents have secondary education while 1.5% and 1.0 had primary education and no formal education respectively. The study further revealed that majority of the respondents had no fixed income (70.5%). 14.5% of the respondents earn average monthly income of below N18,000, 11.0% earn above N18,000 and below N30, 000, while 4.0% earn above N30,000. This simply means that that the respondents in the study area were of low-income earners. The research also discovered that 45.5% of the sampled population are into trading while 30.5% are farmers. 19.0% are civil servants while 5.0% are unemployed. This implies that majority of the population in the study area are into trading and farming. Experiences can be linked to how long one has spent in a place. The survey revealed that majority of the respondents has stayed in the study area for a long period above 25 years (52.0%). The study further revealed that 34.0% have spent between 21 to 25 years in the study areas. This implies that majority of the sampled population are representative of the larger population.

DISTRIBUTIONAL PATTERN OF INFRASTRUCTURAL FACILITIES IN EGUME, THE STUDY AREA

EDUCATIONAL FACILITIES (SCHOOLS)

The study revealed that a total of six primary schools before 2009 in the study area, while in the year 2015, four primary school were established, making a total of ten primary schools. Before 2009 only two secondary schools were in existence, while in the year 2015, another secondary school was established. In the year 2016, one more secondary school was established, making a total of four secondary schools as at the time of this study (Table 2 and Figure 3).

Table 2: School Distribution in Egume between years 2009-2019

PRIMARY SCHOOLS ESTABLISHMENT			
Name	Types	Location	YOE
LGA Primary school	Primary	Efakwu - Egume	Before2009
RCM primary school	Primary	Atecompany - Egume	
CMM L Primary school	Primary	Alokogbe - Egume	
LGA Primary school	Primary	Ogene – Egume	
LGA Primary school	Primary	Ijoji – Egume	
CMML nursery & primary school	Primary	Adumu - Egume	
SS Peter & Paul nursery & primary school	Primary	Atecompany - Egume	Year 2015
CEFN nursery & primary school	Primary	Ijoji – Egume	
Wisdom nursery and primary	Primary	Barack - Egume	
Salvation nursery & primary school	Primary	Efakwu - Egume	
SECONDARY SCHOOLS ESTABLISHMENT			
Community secondary school Egume	secondary	Ojikpadala Abejukolo Road Egume	Before2009
Government secondary school Egume	secondary	Barack Egume	Year 2015
Alokogbe & Ogene secondary school Egume	secondary	Ogene Egume	
SS Peter and Paul Academy	secondary	Atecompany Egume	
			Year 2016

Source: Researcher’s Field Work (2025)

Figure 3: School Distribution in Egume from 2009 to 2019

Source: Researcher’s fieldwork (2025)

The Nearest Neighbour Analysis (NNA) as shown in the probability curve for the distributional pattern for Schools in Egume was discovered to be Random with a p-value

of 0.1(Figure 4). Given the z-score of 1.60376851241, the pattern does not appear to be significantly different than random.

Nearest Neighbour Ratio:	1.224051	
z-score:	1.603769	
p-value:	0.108765	

Figure 4: Average Nearest Neighbour Summary for the Distributional Pattern of Schools in Egume

Source: Researcher’s field work (2025)

The study revealed that only three hospitals were in existence before 2009. In the year 2015 three other hospitals were established.

In the year 2016 two more hospitals were provided in Egume the study area (Figure 5 and Table 3).

HEALTHCARE FACILITIES

Table 3: Health Centres Distribution in Egume from 2009-2019

Name	Location	YOE
Cottage Hospital	Atecompany Egume	Before 2009
Rima Clinic and Maternity	Efekpe	
ST Luke and Maternity	Barack	
LGA Health Dispensary	Ogene	Year 2015
LGA Health Dispensary	Efakwu	
OJ Clinic	Ogene	
Resurrection clinic	Efikpo	Year 2016
LGA Health Dispensary	Ijoji	

Source: Researcher’s field work (2025)

Figure 5: Health Centres Distribution in Egume from 2009 to 2019

Source: Researcher’s Field work, (2025)

The Nearest Neighbour Analysis (NNA) as revealed by the probability curve for the distributional pattern for Health facilities in Egume is Random considered at a p-

value of 0.06 (Figure 6). Given the z-score of 0.448756368625, the pattern does not appear to be significantly different than random. The Average Nearest Neighbour Analysis tool returns five values.

Figure 6: Average Nearest Neighbour Summary for the distributional pattern of Health facilities in Egume

Source: Researcher’s field work (2025)

The study revealed that majority of the respondents (94%) make a journey of above 1km to access the nearest healthcare centre from their homes. 6% of the respondents attest to the fact that they go between 1-5km to access the health centres. The health centres tend to be randomly distributed but

not adequate (table 6). This finding corroborates the study of Adeoye, *et al*, (2011) and Adesiji *et al*, (2012) where it was discovered that inadequacy of infrastructure that can improve the quality of life of the people which is one major factor that impedes rural socioeconomic transformation.

Table 4: Distance travelled to the nearest Healthcare centre

Distance	500-1km	Above 1km	Total
Respondents	20 (10%)	180 (94%)	200 (100%)

Source: Researcher’s field work (2025)

WATER FACILITIES

The sources of water across the study area revealed that 79% of the boreholes are privately owned while 21% are owned by the community. 13.0% of the respondents had community borehole as their source of water while 87% depend on privately

owned. This implies that the sources of water in the study area vary significantly. This finding agrees with the finding of Brown and Chikagbum, (2015) in a study of the challenges of access to infrastructure and social services in selected rural communities in Etche LGA of River State, the result of the findings showed that borehole is a major source of water.

Table 5: Sources and ownership of water supply for the study area

	Private borehole	Community borehole	Total
Source	(87%)	(13%)	200 (100%)
Ownership	(79%)	(21%)	200 (100%)

Source: Researcher’s field work (2025)

As evident in Table 6 and Figure 7, before 2009 two boreholes were in existence in Egume in Dekina LGA of Kogi State, which as discovered from the field work carried out only one of them was functional. No single borehole was dug until years 2016 and 2019

when fifteen boreholes were dug; private individuals dug thirteen while Millennium Development Goals dug two. Furthermore, one out of the thirteen private boreholes were not functional.

Table 6: Borehole Distribution in Egume from 2009 to 2019

S/n	Name	Location	Functionality	YOE
1	MDG Borehole and water Reservoir	Barack-Egume	Functional	Before 2009
2	Owala Borehole and water Reservoir	Owala –Egume	Not Functional	
1	Private Borehole for commercial	Ogene-Egume	Functional	2016-2019
2	Private Borehole for commercial	Ogene-Egume	Functional	
3	Private Borehole for commercial	Ogene-Egume	Functional	
4	Private Borehole for commercial	Ogene-Egume	Functional	
5	Private Borehole for commercial	Efakwu-Egume	Functional	
6	Private Borehole for commercial	Efakwu-Egume	Functional	
7	MDG Borehole and water Reservoir	AlokogbeEgume	Functional	
8	Private Borehole for commercial	Ogene-Egume	Functional	
9	Private Borehole for commercial	Ogene	Functional	
10	Private Borehole for commercial	Efikpo	Functional	
11	Private borehole for commercial	Efikpo	Functional	
12	Private borehole for commercial	Atecompany	Functional	
13	Private borehole for commercial	Alukegbe	Not functional	
14	MDG Borehole and water Reservoir	Alukegbe	Functional	
15	Private borehole for commercial	Ijoji	Functional	

Source: Researcher’s field work (2025)

Figure 7: Borehole Distribution in Egume from 2009 to 2019
Source: Researcher’s field work (2025)

The Nearest Neighbour Analysis (NNA) as seen from the probability curve, shows that the distributional pattern for Boreholes in Egume, the study area is Clustered considered at a p-value of 0.09 (Figure 8). Given the z-score of -1.6559341036, there is

less than 10% likelihood that this clustered pattern could be the result of random chance. The Average Nearest Neighbour Analysis tool returns five values: Observed Mean Distance, Expected Mean Distance, Nearest Neighbour Index, z-score, and p-value. These values are accessible from the Results window of the ArcGIS Software.

Figure 8: Average Nearest Neighbour Summary for the distributional pattern Boreholes in the study area

Source: Researcher’s field work (2025)

The study discovered as presented on table 8 that 49% of the respondents get their water from a distance of above one kilometre, some 1km and some a distance of 500meters. This implies that water sources within the study area are not randomly distributed but clustered. The results showed that inequalities exist in varying degrees with the distribution of infrastructural facilities in the study area. This result corroborates the work

of Adefila (2008) where he discovered that a marked spatial variation in infrastructural development in Plateau State of Nigeria were revealed. The implication here is that there will be disparity in the living standard and this is not a surprise because spatial inequality in infrastructure among regions has existed since the dawn of civilization (Aderamo and Aina, 2011; Madu, 2012).

Table 7: Distance Travelled to Water Sources

	Less than 500M	Above 500-1Km	Above 1Km?	Total
Respondents	28%	23%	49%	100%

Source: Researcher’s field work (2025)

ELECTRICITY SUPPLY FACILITIES

With reference to electricity supply, the study revealed as presented in Table 8, that 60% of the respondents depend on National grid

supply for their energy, 30% use generator and 10% depend on solar. This implies that majority of the respondent in Egume depend majorly on national grid.

Table 8: Sources of Electricity

SOURCE	national grid	generator supply	solar supply	Total
Respondents	60%	30%	10%	100

Source: Researcher’s field work (2025)

The study observed that a total number of seven transformers were provided in the study area at different periods, this is shown in Figure 9 and table 9. Before 2009 a total of

six transformers were provided and installed in the study area while in the year 2015 only one transformer was provided in the study area (Figure 9 and Table 9).

Figure 9: Transformer Distribution in Egume from 2009 to 2019

Source: Researcher’s field work (2025)

Table 9: Transformer Distribution in Egume from 2009-2019

Name	Location	Year of Establishment
Transformer	Efakwu	Before 2009
Transformer	Market square	
Transformer	Ogene	
Transformer	Alukogbe	
Transformer	RCM	
Transformer	Ijoji	
Transformer	Efakwu Along Acharu bypass Rd	Year 2015

Source: Researcher’s field work (2025)

The nearest neighbour analysis explains that the distributional pattern of the transformers. Given the z-score of 3.73775312405, there is less than 1% likelihood that this dispersed pattern could be the result of random

chance. The probability curve for the distributional pattern of transformers for electricity distribution in the study area shows dispersed distribution at $\alpha 0.00$ but considered Random at a p-value of 0.05. (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Average Nearest Neighbour Summary for the Distributional pattern for

Electricity in Egume

Source: Researcher’s field work (2025)

FACTORS RESPONSIBLE FOR THE PROVISION OF INFRASTRUCTURE IN THE STUDY AREA

The mean score as discovered by the study and presented on table 10 revealed that; for political reason, the scale gave 1.6 which is less than 2.60 on likert scale was rejected meaning that infrastructure in the community were not there as a result of political reasons. Profit making was 2.6 which is still lower than the accepted value, meaning that the respondents does not agree with that. Security reasons have a scale of 1.8 also rejected, Traditional rulers’ decision gave a

likert mean score of 3.2 and this was accepted meaning that respondents were in agreement that most of the infrastructures were attracted by the traditional rulers. The mean score for Community development was 2.0. This was rejected, meaning that the respondents were not satisfied with the variable. The mean score for government decisions was 1.3 this was rejected, meaning that government efforts have not yielded any result. 1.6 of likert mean score for respondents that are not certain is below the accepted point, pointed to the fact that, some respondents does not know what was going on in their community.

Table 10: Reasons for the location of Infrastructures in the study area

QUESTIONNAIRE ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	DECISION
Political reason	88 (57.5)%	42 (27.5)%	23 (15)%	0 (0)%	1.6	Rejected
For Profit making	70 (45.75)%	28(18.3)%	32 (20.9)%	23 (15)%	2.6	Rejected
Security reason	65 (42.80)%	60 (39)%	18 (11.80)%	10 (6.5)%	1.8	Rejected
Traditional Rulers Decision	15 (9.8)%	10 (6.5)%	63 (41)%	65 (42.8)%	3.2	Accepted
Community Development	93 (60.8)%	37(24.2)%	15 (9.8)%	8 (3.2)%	2.0	Rejected
Government Decision	125 (81.7)%	15 (9.8)%	13 (8.5)%	0 (0)%	1.3	Rejected
Not certain	98 (64)%	25 (16.3)%	20 (13)%	10 (6.5)%	1.6	Rejected

SA: Strongly Agreed. A: Agreed. D: Disagreed. SD: Strongly Disagreed.

Lerkert Scale: 1.00—2.60 (Rejected) 2.61—5.00(Accepted)

Source: Researcher’s field work (2025)

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings, Egume has some rural infrastructures provided and attracted by the traditional rulers which are randomly distributed. Impact of infrastructure development in the rural areas is not only focused on the physical development but at the same time, concerns the efforts in

improving the quality of life of the rural communities. The infrastructure development in the rural areas requires collaboration and integration between all related parties especially the Government and the community social workers. The collaboration of the related parties and the rural communities are essential in achieving success in the rural community development programmes.

Based on the findings the study recommended that proper attention of the government is needed on the provision of infrastructural facilities in the study area and other rural areas as well. It was also discovered that some of these infrastructures are clustered, therefore, distribution of infrastructure should also be done with equity and fairness in order to avoid lopsidedness.

Infrastructure development in the rural areas is not only focused on the physical

development but concerned in the efforts of improving the quality of life of the rural people. The infrastructural development in the rural areas requires collaboration and integration between all related parties especially the Government and the community social workers. The collaboration of the related parties and the rural communities are essential in achieving success in the rural community development programmes.

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